

Assay of Memantine Hydrochloride by UV Spectrophotometer

Asra Ali Bahazeq¹, Wasfiya Noor Syeda¹, Nashra Fatima Isba¹, MD. Muzaffar-Ur-Rehman^{*1}, Uzma Amatul Baqi²

¹Department of Pharmaceutical chemistry, Sultan-ul-uloom College of Pharmacy, Banjara Hills, Hyderabad, Telangana, India-500034.

² Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis, RBVRR Women's college of Pharmacy, Barkathpura, Hyderabad, Telangana 500027.
Email_id: m.muzaffar687@gmail.com
Contact: 8686294437

ABSTRACT - Memantine hydrochloride is a class of N-Methyl-D-Aspartase receptor antagonist used in the treatment of Alzheimer's disease. The main aim of the present study was to develop a method to determine Memantine hydrochloride in tablet formulation which is simple, sensitive, precise and economical as per ICH guidelines. The method was validated at λ_{max} of 254nm. Beer-Lambert's was obeyed between the concentration ranges of 0.2-0.6 μ g/ml. A good linear relationship with correlation coefficient of 0.998 was obtained and the LOD and LOQ values were 0.48 μ g/ml and 1.48 μ g/ml respectively. The method was also employed on the tablet formulation (Namenda) and the recovery was found to be 99.8%.

Keywords: Memantine hydrochloride, Alzheimer's disease, ICH guidelines, Validation,

INTRODUCTION

Memantine hydrochloride, chemically known as 3,5-dimethyladamantan-1-amine;hydrochloride, with the molecular formula of C₁₂H₂₁N.HCl and molecular weight 215.765g/mol, is the first drug to be approved by US FDA, manufactured as Namenda by Forest Pharmaceuticals.^[1-2] It has been widely used to treat cognitive symptoms of Alzheimer's disease such as memory loss, confusion, problems with thinking and reasoning.^[3-7] It acts as antagonist to Glutamatergic NMDA receptor^[8-9] which is responsible for cognitive symptoms and also at 5-HT₃^[10] where it acts as anti-emetic. Literature study reveals several assay methods for determining the drug by HPLC^[11], and spectrofluorimetry^[12] techniques. Its determination in the rat and human plasma were also noted by derivatized fluorimetric^[13] and mass spectroscopic^[14] methods respectively. In the present study, the developed method was validated as per ICH guidelines^[15] to determine the presence Memantine hydrochloride in bulk and tablet formulation (Namenda) using methanol as a solvent. The method was found to be economical, simple and precise. The detection by UV spectroscopy was done at the absorption maxima (λ_{max}) of 254nm.

Figure 1: Structure of Memantine Hydrochloride

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Instrumentation and reagents

Memantine hydrochloride was obtained as a gift sample from Chandra labs, Hyderabad, Telangana, India. Nicolet Evolution 100 UV-Visible spectrophotometer empowered with Vision Pro software was used to determine the absorption maxima. Methanol of HPLC grade was used as solvent. 0.45 μ filter paper, used for filtering the solutions prepared, was purchased from Millipore. Tablet formulation of Memantine hydrochloride (Namenda) was purchased from nearby local pharmacy.

Preparation of Standard Stock Solution for Memantine hydrochloride

Weighed amount of 100mg of the Memantine drug was mixed in methanol and sonicated for 5 minutes to dissolve the drug completely and filtered through 0.45 μ filter paper. It was then diluted up to the mark in a 100ml volumetric flask of which 10ml was pipette out and diluted to 100ml with methanol. 1ml of this solution was then pipette and dissolved in 10ml volumetric flask and made up the volume with the solvent to obtain 10 μ g/ml. From this, required dilutions were made to get the concentration of 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6 μ g/ml.

Preparation of Sample Solution for Memantine

Twenty tablets were taken and crushed into fine powder. An accurately weighed amount of powder equivalent to 5mg of Memantine drug was taken and dissolved in methanol and made up to the mark of a 50ml volumetric flask. From this solution, required dilutions were done to get the final concentration of 10 μ g/ml.

The concentration of Memantine was determined by measuring absorbance of the sample at 254nm and values were substituted in the following formula to obtain concentrations.

$$\%Assay = \frac{\text{Mean Test absorbance}}{\text{Mean standard absorbance}} \times \frac{\text{Dilution of standard}}{\text{Dilution of sample}} \times \frac{\text{Mean Test weight}}{\text{Label claim}} \times \text{Potency of standard}$$

Figure 2: UV spectra of Memantine hydrochloride

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Linearity

Linearity was checked by preparing standard solutions at five different concentrations, ranging from 0.2-0.6 μ g/ml of Memantine at 254nm, Calibration curves (n=5) were plotted in the range 0.2-0.6 μ g/ml between absorbance taken on y-axis and concentration of drug on x-axis. The results of linearity study of Memantine measured in Methanol are shown in Table 1 and calibration curve is shown in figure 3.

TABLE 1: ABSORBANCE OF DIFFERENT CONC OF MEMANTINE

S.no	Concentrations(μ g/ml)	Absorbance
1	0.2	0.208
2	0.3	0.310
3	0.4	0.419
4	0.5	0.502
5	0.6	0.614

Figure 3: Linearity of Memantine hydrochloride

Accuracy

To check the accuracy of the developed method and to study the interference of formulation excipients, analytical recovery experiments were carried out by using standard addition method, at 100% levels. Percentage recovery of the drug was calculated from the total amount of drug found. The results reveal no interference of excipients.

Recovery & Precision

The method to be precise was determined by analyzing variation of results within the same day (intraday) and between the days (interday). The samples were checked for absorbance for 5 times at 254nm on the same day as well as on different days and RSD was found to be less than 1%. Table 2 shows the result of the precision and recovery studies.

TABLE 2: RESULTS OF RECOVERY STUDIES OF MEMANTINE BY Q-ANALYSIS METHOD (INTRADAY & INTERDAY)

Drug	Amount added	% Recovery	SD (n=3)
Memantine (Intraday)	2mcg	101.25	0.77
Memantine (Interday)	1mcg	100.99	0.73
Drug	Labelled Amount (mg)	Amount Found in Mg	% Recovery
Memantine	5mg	4.96mg	99.8

Sensitivity

Limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantitation (LOQ) of the developed method were calculated using the following equations;

$$LOD=3.3\sigma/s \text{ and } LOQ=10\sigma/s$$

Where,

σ = Standard deviation from calibration curve

S = slope of regression equation.

Results are shown in Table 3.

TABLE 3: VALIDATION RESULTS OBTAINED BY THE ADOPTED METHOD

PARAMETER	254nm
Beer's law limits (mcg)	0.2-0.6 µg
Molar absorptivity (1/mol/cm)	19071.19046
Correlation coefficient (R ²)	0.998
Regression Equation (Y)	y = 1.004x + 0.009
Slope, b	1.004
Intercept, c	0.009
Standard deviation	0.149
Limit Of Detection (LOD)	0.48 µg/ml
Limit Of Quantification (LOQ)	1.48 µg/ml

CONCLUSION

The proposed method was found to be simple, sensitive, and precise. A good linear relationship with correlation co-efficient of 0.9984 was obtained. The developed method was found to be accurate as the recovery of the sample was more than 99%. Therefore, validated the method can be successfully employed for the routine analysis of Memantine hydrochloride in tablet as well as bulk formulation as the method is economical and avoids expensive equipments.

REFERENCES

- [1] Witt A, Macdonald N, Kirkpatrick P. Memantine hydrochloride. *Nat Rev Drug Discov* 2004; 3:109–10.
- [2] Kilpatrick GJ, Tilbrook GS. Memantine. *Merz. Current opinion in investigational drugs* (London, England: 2000). 2002; 3(5):798-806.
- [3] Mobius HJ, Stoffler A, Graham SM. Memantine hydrochloride: pharmacological and clinical profile. *Drugs of Today*. 2004; 40(8):685-96.
- [4] Moretti R, Torre P, Antonello RM, Cattaruzza T, Pizzolato G. Memantine: Its Role in Vascular Dementia. *Drug Design Reviews-Online*. 2005; 2(6):449-56.
- [5] Möbius HJ. Memantine: update on the current evidence. *International journal of geriatric psychiatry*. 2003; 18(S1).
- [6] Ferris SH. Evaluation of memantine for the treatment of Alzheimer's disease. *Expert opinion on pharmacotherapy*. 2003; 4(12):2305-13.
- [7] Kornhuber J, Kennepohl EM, Bleich S, Wiltfang J, Kraus T, Reulbach U, Meineke I. Memantine pharmacotherapy. *Clinical pharmacokinetics*. 2007; 46(7):599-612.
- [8] Winblad B, Möbius HJ, Stöfler A. Glutamate receptors as a target for Alzheimer's disease—are clinical results supporting the hope? *In Ageing and Dementia Current and Future Concepts 2002* (pp. 217-225). Springer, Vienna.
- [9] Losi G, Lanza M, Makovec F, Artusi R, Caselli G, Puia G. Functional in vitro characterization of CR 3394: A novel voltage dependent N-methyl-d-aspartate (NMDA) receptor antagonist. *Neuropharmacology*. 2006; 50(3):277-85.
- [10] Rammes G, Rupprecht R, Ferrari U, Zieglgänsberger W, Parsons CG. The N-methyl-D-aspartate receptor channel blockers memantine, MRZ 2/579 and other amino-alkyl-cyclohexanes antagonise 5-HT₃ receptor currents in cultured HEK-293 and N1E-115 cell systems in a non-competitive manner. *Neuroscience letters*. 2001; 306(1-2):81-4.
- [11] Narola B, Singh AS, Santhakumar PR, Chandrashekar TG. A validated stability-indicating reverse phase HPLC assay method for the determination of memantine hydrochloride drug substance with UV-detection using precolumn derivatization technique. *Analytical chemistry insights*. 2010; 5: ACI-S3936.
- [12] Michail K, Daabees H, Beltagy Y, Abdel-Khalek M, Khamis M. Spectrophotometric and spectrofluorimetric determination of memantine hydrochloride in bulk and pharmaceutical preparations. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2011; 3(3):180-5.
- [13] Xie MF, Zhou W, Tong XY, Chen YL, Cai Y, Li Y, Duan GL. High performance liquid chromatographic determination of memantine hydrochloride in rat plasma using sensitive fluorometric derivatization. *Journal of separation science*. 2011; 34(3):241-6.
- [14] Leis HJ, Fauler G, Windischhofer W. Quantitative analysis of memantine in human plasma by gas chromatography/negative ion chemical ionization/mass spectrometry. *Journal of mass spectrometry*. 2002; 37(5):477-80.
- [15] Guideline IH. Validation of analytical procedures: text and methodology Q2 (R1). In *International Conference on Harmonization*, Geneva, Switzerland 2005 Nov (pp. 11-12).